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THE TRANSLATOR'S SKILL IN THE UZBEK TRANSLATION OF "A FAREWELL TO ARMS"

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Annotatsiya: *This article provides information about translation and the renowned Uzbek translator Ibrahim Gafurov's views as a translator, focusing on his translation of Ernest Hemingway's "A Farewell to Arms" into Uzbek.*

Keywords: *Uzbek translators, A Farewell to Arms, translation, originality, approaches, cultural background, culture, dimensions*

МАСТЕРСТВО ПЕРЕВОДЧИКА В УЗБЕКСКОМ ПЕРЕВОДЕ «ПРОЩАЙ, ОРУЖИЕ»

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Аннотация: *В этой статье представлена информация о переводе и взглядах известного узбекского переводчика Ибрагима Гафурова как переводчика, уделяя особое внимание его переводу «Прощай, оружие» Эрнеста Хемингуэя на узбекский язык.*

Ключевые слова: *узбекские переводчики, «Прощай, оружие», перевод, оригинальность, подходы, культурный фон, культура, измерения*

The task of translating a work from one language to another necessitates a deep understanding of both linguistic and stylistic elements, as well as contextual considerations, to maintain meaning and appropriate expression. It requires extensive experience, in-depth knowledge, and a meticulous approach.

According to Gofurov and a group of other scholars, translation is a type of literary creation that consists of recreating linguistic units in a new language, from documents, texts, manuscripts, works of art, to proverbs and sayings in a particular language. Translation is considered one of the most important manifestations of interethnic communication. As early as the time of the oldest communities, the process of translation arose due to the need for interaction between people, communication, and until today this area has become polished throughout its development and has time to gain its place and importance in various aspects of our life. The concept of “translation” refers to the process of

turning a certain text or work from one language to another, as well as a finished translation work.

Today, in modern Uzbek translation of the 21st century, many talented translators and linguists carry out certain work in the direction of translation. Among them, Muhammad Ali, Ibrahim Gafurov, Najmiddin Komilov are listed. While translating works into another language, there are several main dimensions at the heart of comparative analysis. First, translation strategies vary widely among translators. Most translators view word-for-word translation into the original Uzbek text optimally, and in this context they attempt to preserve the linguistic structure of the text as well as its lexical meaningfulness. Others aim to deliver to the reader in a way that resonates the basic meaning and culturally the characters of the chosen text. Furthermore, these approaches in the field of translation that can have a good effect on how translated texts or works are perceived and understood by other peoples and nations.

As the translator focuses on the translation of a text, one will have the ability to reflect both thoughts and views in his or her own mind in the translation of that text, taking into account the lexical grammatical elements in that text, as well as aspects of lingua cultural and historians. Nowadays, there are various methods of translating texts and documents related to the work of art and other types of translation by translators, which are used in the translation process.

While having a look at the translated works of Ibrahim Gafurov, it should be noted that he is a master of translation. Once he mentioned that the problem of translation is, first and foremost, a reader's problem. The translator primarily considers their reader and their cultural background. While some writers create solely for themselves, disregarding the reader, they are a minority. Translators, writers, and scholars, however, strive to maintain and strengthen their connection with their audience. They are eager to see the impact their hard work has on others. This interaction fosters the growth of both the creator and the reader, encouraging active engagement. Yet, author-reader interaction remains surprisingly limited, a situation neither beneficial nor praiseworthy.

The translation of Hemingway's "A Farewell to Arms" into Uzbek, translator paid great attention to the preservation of the original in translation of metonymy, which is one of the most complex types of migration when he was translating the works into Uzbek. It is observed that the original on the basis can find an alternative option, give it its meaning and content characteristics or form stored or modified, using more scientific translation methods than transliteration, annotation and artistic translation. In the process of translation, he attempts to

preserve the content of the text, artistic originality and artistic coloritis of the work, and while creative approaches in this regard were observed, the translator made minor flaws, in most cases, could not preserve some artistic image tools, lexical and contextual meanings of national words and phrases, as well as pictorial compactness, musical melodiousness. And the reason for this is the fact that he adheres to the principle of more scientific and free translation. A translator translating from another language, ignoring every small detail, commonality and originality, may undermine the nationality of the work, and the work of art may not correctly convey the individual style and spirit of the author to the reader. A translator who studied well the traditions, lifestyle, spirit, culture, mentality and language of the English people was able to fully give the content of the original in translation through metonymy. The translation of "A Farewell to Arms" into Uzbek serves as an auxiliary resource for the Uzbek reader to create an idea of the English people's about a certain period such as World war, way of life, culture, mentality, national character. National realities have been turned by transliteration or equivalent application, which is defined by the fact that the translation language cannot absorb the quality, causing misunderstandings for the reader. This method, which the translator used, is the most correct, which in front of the Uzbek reader views where the event took place.

However, the translator who rendered "A Farewell to Arms" into Russian, Yevgeniy Kalashnikov, successfully captured Hemingway's central theme: a denouncement of horror of the war. Kalashnikov's translation reached a level of excellence that matched the original English text. Ibrahim Gafurov then used this translation as a basis for his Uzbek version.

Taking into consideration, the task of translating a work of art from one language to another via a third language is extraordinarily difficult, risky, and complex; demanding great responsibility and bravery. However, Ibrahim Gafurov's profound understanding of Hemingway's style and work made the task achievable.

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Nashr tillari: O‘zbek, Rus, Ingliz va Qoraqalpoq tillari

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